

RUMIYYA JAMALOVA. CONTINUOUS ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION: MODERN SCIENTIFIC AND PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES IN THE TEACHING OF CHEMISTRY AND THE ENLIGHTENMENT OF YOUTH (pp. 18-27)

METHODOLOGY AND TEACHING TECHNOLOGY

CONTINUOUS ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION: MODERN SCIENTIFIC AND PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES IN THE TEACHING OF CHEMISTRY AND THE ENLIGHTENMENT OF YOUTH

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Abstract. The article discusses issues related to continuous environmental education in the process of teaching chemistry, modern pedagogical approaches to this priority field, and the development of youth in the context of sustainable growth, environmental risks, ways of reducing them, and the formation of an eco-conscious individual. It also addresses the need to cultivate young people with clear thinking, flexibility, competence, communication culture, mathematical and computer literacy, social skills, broad knowledge across fields, the ability to express themselves in the cultural sphere, and entrepreneurial abilities to solve global problems. Furthermore, the article mentions that an ordinary person living in countries with the highest Human Development Index (HDI) is responsible for about four times more carbon dioxide emissions and approximately twice as many other significant greenhouse gas emissions compared to a person living in countries with low, medium, or high HDI levels.

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Introduction

Throughout the 21st century, the evolving society is becoming increasingly aware that human sustainable development and the planet's sustainability challenges have turned the issue of preserving Earth's resources into an urgent matter linked to global economic development. "At first glance, this problem may seem somewhat ambitious. However, from a historical perspective, economic development clearly demonstrates with evidence that the rapid progress initiated by the Industrial Revolution and the advancement of technologies has not left the natural environment unaffected. Countless means of transportation, production processes, telecommunications and digital technologies, as well as synthetic chemistry and nanotechnologies, appeal to the tastes of today's society. People are satisfied with the highly developed lifestyle, working conditions, and the features brought by the 21st century. [UN, **Human Development Program, 2016**]

Today, the world has become a single global village, seemingly resting in the palm of our hand. We have almost forgotten the environmental problems we face and the ecological risks for which we bear responsibility. We have also lost sight of our accountability to Mother Nature who provides all the goods and services essential for human development while much of human activity continues to disrupt, damage, or attempt to reshape natural systems. Humanity must never forget that it has only one place to live.

"That place is this planet, and it is obliged to protect this trust and pass it on to future generations in the name of sustainable development. The importance of this responsibility demands that we, as educators, enlighten learners in classrooms and lecture halls. It requires us to cultivate young people who are clear-thinking, adaptable, competent, culturally communicative, mathematically and digitally literate, socially

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skilled, well- informed in all fields, capable of expressing themselves in cultural domains, and equipped with entrepreneurial abilities. This has now become a necessity of our time. Time is passing rapidly, and throughout the entire educational process during supplementary activities, trainings, seminars, conferences, and round-table discussions it is essential to implement continuous environmental education aimed at shaping an “eco- human” who understands the ecosystem. Within the framework of modern scientific and pedagogical approaches, issues related to raising young people’s awareness of sustainable development should be discussed, and education for sustainable development should be effectively implemented.

Main part. At the same time, addressing these issues requires defining common goals and objectives, planned outcomes, the content of the teaching and educational process, and their implementation through appropriate technologies. The main purpose of this requirement is to understand and explain the vital relationship between economic activity and nature, to generate new knowledge for making better and wiser decisions, and to use this knowledge purposefully in the teaching and educational process.

Let us pay attention to the ants gathered around a single drop of water. In this scene, which evokes pleasant feelings in each of us, the drop of water containing the reflection of the entire world can be compared to the planet Earth, while the ants surrounding it resemble humans. Then a question arises: why can we not share this small sphere?

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Are we not even as humble and united as these tiny creatures? If we look at the facts, the answer to this question will become clear on its own.

In the last 600 years, there have been 14,513 wars in the world.

- 3.64 billion people have died in these wars.
- Nearly 570 million people do not have enough to eat.
- Almost 3 billion people do not have regular access to clean water.
- Every year, 750,000 people die from waterborne diseases.
- 800 million inhabitants of our planet are illiterate.
- 250 million children under the age of 14 do not attend school.

These facts reveal the cruelty of humankind and bring to light even greater and more pressing global issues faced by people around the world. [UN Human Development Programme, 2016]

Among these facts, the most striking are poverty, the imbalance between countries, hunger, poor health and diseases, polluted water, lack of sanitation, and low levels of education. Other major concerns include children being unable to attend school, insufficient employment opportunities and low-income jobs, weak economic growth where a country lacks the budget to meet the needs of its people and gender inequality, which manifests as unequal treatment and limited opportunities for women and men.

Wars, conflicts, and instability lead to insecurity, violence against individuals, injustice, corruption, and violations of human rights. Many countries fail to build relationships based on mutual cooperation and agreements, disrupting global harmony and people's well-being.

Additional global challenges include energy shortages, weak infrastructure, underdeveloped technology and communication systems, cities and villages located in hazardous areas, and unstable living conditions. Resource depletion and the inability

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to reuse lost materials, climate change, and the pollution of seas and oceans also contribute to the crisis. Furthermore, the abandonment of certain settlements, limited access to technological tools, the high cost of phones and computers, lack of personal safety, population growth, obesity, racism, and the disappearance of small towns are among the most pressing issues facing humanity today.

Naturally, in order to overcome these problems, every individual must use their unique abilities and bring forward creative ideas. This issue can be effectively addressed through the modern teaching methods of chemistry. The role of chemistry in improving human welfare and quality of life depends on the quantity and quality of food, water, energy, and biological resources, as well as on ensuring sustainability at local, national, and global levels. These relationships can be explored through the teaching of various topics such as hydrocarbons, carbohydrates, amino acids, proteins, and polymers. [Aliyev & Azizov, 2006]

During the teaching of organic chemistry topics, research activities, projects, and presentations can be designed to direct students' attention to the aspects and principles of the human development concept, enabling them to understand the essence of the idea of a "human revolution." Through such influence, learners can be guided to prioritize moral values over mere accumulation of material wealth, to recognize the importance of creating conditions for the full realization of human creative potential, to highlight ecological priorities in production processes, to uphold social justice and political and economic freedom as the highest social values, to promote cultural enlightenment, and to comprehend how the role of the individual is being qualitatively renewed in the modern world.

By conveying these ideas, it becomes possible to develop the essential skills of an "eco-human." To lay the foundation for such competencies, it is important to ensure the integrated inclusion of environmental topics when planning instructional units,

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thereby fostering the creation of new knowledge. In subjects related to oil refining, the development of new skills should be linked with environmental considerations, combining them with the principles of freedom of opportunity, process freedom, and justice. [UN Human Development Programme, 2016]

Learners should first seek to answer the question, “How does the environment become polluted?” and present their own reasoning:

- ✓ Oil spills
- ✓ Vehicle emissions
- ✓ Polyethylene bags
- ✓ Landfills
- ✓ Power plants operating on underground fuels
- ✓ Air travel
- ✓ Chemical agents used in agriculture and industrial contamination of water

When exploring the connection of these factors to chemistry, the idea that “*humanity is part of nature, and life depends heavily on the continuous processes of nature*” becomes evident, clearly highlighting the crucial role chemistry plays in human life.

During the teaching of chemistry, directing learners’ attention to the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) is one of the most effective methods of raising awareness. Environmental initiatives such as preventing desertification, the expansion of saline soils, and deforestation; conserving and enriching biodiversity; implementing preventive measures against floods, landslides, and other natural disasters; mitigating ecological risks; protecting national parks, reserves, and coastal areas; and ensuring the sustainability of pastures should be communicated to and supported by the audience.

According to UN projections, the world population will reach 9.5 billion by 2050. This growth necessitates new thinking and knowledge to stabilize population levels and reduce pressure on the environment. Countries with developed and transitional

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economies must adopt advanced technologies to reduce pollution caused by vehicles, industrial enterprises, and other sources.

Developed countries, in turn, are required to reconsider their consumption patterns. Studies show that although only one-fifth of the world's population lives in developed countries, they consume 70% of global energy resources, 75% of metal resources, and 85% of forest resources. "Consumption often occurs at the expense of developing countries, which host the industrial enterprises supplying these resources and generating environmental pollution, and consequently bear the negative ecological consequences. From this perspective, it is important to consider the principle of fair distribution of benefits and harms within the context of sustainable development." If we focus on analyzing the relationship between consumption, sustainability, and human development, what do we observe? An example of unfair ecological responsibility is the carbon dioxide emissions attributed to a country's economic development and its impact on the climate. Currently, an average person living in countries with the highest Human Development Index (HDI) is responsible for approximately four times more CO₂ emissions and about twice as much of other significant greenhouse gas emissions than an average person living in countries with low, medium, or high HDI. On the other hand, what role does trade play? Trade often enables developed countries to transfer environmentally harmful production to developing countries. [Murphy, C.N., 2006]

On the other hand, environmental degradation affects people in several ways:

- It can deprive individuals of the means to live, impact their health, and leave them vulnerable to natural disasters.
- The reduction of arable land and water-related problems contributes to food insecurity.

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Unsafe drinking water, inadequate sanitation, and indoor air pollution are the most serious environmental factors affecting human health, particularly in countries with low Human Development Index (HDI) values.

To visualize the negative impacts of human activity on the environment, let us consider some examples. For instance, the pollution of water bodies with wastewater is closely linked to the increasing use of water in various industrial sectors. Water used in technological processes becomes contaminated with harmful substances such as petroleum products, acids, phenols, synthetic detergents, oils, and organic compounds before eventually entering natural water bodies. As an example, the amount of polluted water generated by a medium-capacity dairy plant (processing 50 tons of milk per shift) is equivalent to the wastewater produced by a settlement with a population of 15,000 people.

The atmosphere has become heavily polluted with various harmful substances. The main types of atmospheric pollution are gaseous and particulate combustion products. As a result of burning different types of fuels, 150 million tons of sulfur dioxide, 200 million tons of carbon oxides, 50 million tons of hydrocarbons, 53 million tons of nitrogen oxides, and other pollutants enter the atmosphere each year. Overall, nearly 2.5 billion tons of various substances are released into the Earth's atmosphere annually. Even with good intentions, human activity causes harm to nature. The goal is to make these activities less damaging, prevent harm where possible, and mitigate their effects. To analyze the impacts of human activity on ecosystems, United Nations research identifies four main groups of ecosystem services: *provisioning, regulating, cultural, and supporting services*.

Provisioning services include fruits, vegetables, timber, fish, and livestock. In addition to food, provisioning services encompass drinking water, wood, fuel, oils, plants that can be used for clothing and accessories, and medicinal resources.

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Regulating services provide numerous essential functions that make life possible for humans. Plants purify air and water, bacteria decompose waste, insects and bees pollinate flowers, and tree roots prevent erosion and stabilize soil.

Within cultural services, ecosystems guide human life as a constant force for cultural, intellectual, and social development. By establishing a healthy relationship with nature, we can witness how the natural world transforms both the planet and humanity.

Conclusion

Thus, in the teaching of chemistry, modern scientific and pedagogical approaches ensure continuous ecological education on the basis of the principle of humanism. As a result of this principle, the world's global problems—the Sustainable Development Goals are provided with person-centered, responsible, and lifelong learning opportunities.

Throughout the entire educational process, during the implementation of additional activities such as trainings, seminars, conferences, and round tables, continuous ecological education is carried out for the formation of an eco-human who understands the ecosystem, and modern scientific-pedagogical approaches to the issues of raising youth awareness about sustainable development are discussed, with education for sustainable development being implemented. The most important aspect of learning for life is ecosystem services: provisioning, regulating, cultural, and supporting services.

Within supporting services, ecosystems provide essential functions such as photosynthesis, nutrient cycling, soil formation, and the water cycle, ensuring the continuity of natural processes. These processes make it possible to sustain the Earth's

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fundamental life forms. All of this requires serious education and awareness. “For the better future of our children, we must protect our planet; I hope this universal goal will unite us for the sake of future generations.”

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